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The development strategy of women farmer groups (KWT) in the urban farming program at Palembang City

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Abstract

The Women Farmers Group (KWT) is a participatory forum formed to empower women, especially in the field of agriculture and household-scale food management. The Women Farmers Group (KWT) plays a strategic role as a driving force for community-based urban farming. Bukit Kecil and Plaju sub-districts are two sub-districts in Palembang City which are dominated by residential and urban areas and have Women Farmers Group (KWT) that actively manages Urban Farming activities. The objectives of this study are to analyze the role of Women Farmer Groups (KWT) in urban farming programs before and after assistance. The sample sampling method used in this study is the census method, because the number of populations involved in the study is relatively small (less than 100 people) so that more accurate and distributive data can be obtained. The number of samples in this study is 40 people, 27 members of KWT Cempako and 13 members of KWT Barokah. The results of this study show that the development strategy of KWT Cempako and KWT Barokah in the urban farming program in Palembang City is in quadrant 1. The location of the strategic coordinates in Quadrant I indicates that the internal conditions of KWT have been able to support the optimal use of opportunities.

Keywords: Agricultural Extension; Community Empowerment; SWOT; Urban Farming; Women Farmer Groups

1. Introduction

Food security is a strategic issue that is closely related to human survival, social stability, and economic development of a country. According to the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), food security is achieved when all people, at all times, have physical, social, and economic access to sufficient, safe, and nutritious food to meet their living needs and food preferences [1].

In Indonesia, food security is still a major challenge despite various policies that have been implemented, such as food diversification, strengthening food reserves, and protecting local farmers. Based on the Global Food Security Index (GFSI) in 2023, Indonesia is ranked 63rd out of 113 countries, which shows that there is still a need to improve the availability, access, quality, and resilience of the food system to shocks. This shows that food security is not only determined by agricultural production, but also includes aspects of distribution, accessibility, price stability, and environmental sustainability [2].

South Sumatra Province has great natural resource potential to support a sustainable food security system. This potential includes the extent of agricultural land, the existence of swampland that can be optimized as suboptimal land, to a strategic geographical position that supports the smooth distribution of food between regions [3]. However, the food sector in this region is inseparable from various serious challenges, especially due to rapid urbanization, conversion of agricultural land into non-productive land, climate change, and vulnerability of distribution supply chains. The disparity between the potential and realization of food security is also evident in various districts/cities.

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The city of Palembang has a very strategic position in the regional food system of South Sumatra. As a center of government, economy, and trade, Palembang plays a role as the main distribution node as well as the largest consumption area in the province. Palembang relies on commodity supply staple foods from various production center areas, both from within the provinces such as East OKU and Banyuasin, as well as from outside the provinces such as Lampung and West Java. This dependence makes Palembang vulnerable to distribution disruptions, price spikes, and supply shortages, especially for staple commodities such as rice, chili, and eggs [4].

Along with the development of the trade, services, industry, and infrastructure sectors, the city of Palembang is experiencing a rapid urbanization rate. This urbanization is characterized by an increase in the number of people in urban areas, the expansion of residential areas, and the conversion of land from agriculture to built land [4].

The population of Palembang City in 2023 will reach more than 1.7 million people, an increase from around 1.4 million people in 2010. This growth is not only due to the natural birth rate, but is also triggered by migration flows from rural areas in South Sumatra to urban centers. This urbanization has led to an increase in the need for housing, transportation facilities, clean water, and food availability [4].

Along with increasing urbanization, agricultural land in Palembang City is getting narrower due to land conversion, while food needs continue to increase. This condition demands alternative solutions to increase food security in urban areas. One of the approaches that is developing is urban farming. Urban farming is a food production activity carried out in urban areas, both on open land and narrow land, by utilizing appropriate technology and innovation [5].

Urban farming is a gardening concept that utilizes space in homes or settlements. The tendency of Indonesian people to gather and socialize can be used as a basis for forming communities that provide benefits in urban areas. The yard area of the house can be used for agriculture, especially vegetable crops that are easy to grow and have affordable costs, supporting the implementation of the program by maximizing the agricultural facilities used, in accordance with the concept of effective and efficient [6].

Urban farming is considered to be able to make a real contribution to food security, especially in terms of the availability and access to fresh food for urban communities. In addition, urban farming also supports strengthening the household economy, efficiency of narrow land use, and increasing environmental awareness of urban communities (Putri & Nugroho, 2023). Research also shows that urban farming practices can shorten food supply chains and increase the resilience of local food systems to external shocks.

Urban farming directly provides food, especially fresh vegetables, in the residential environment. Households are no longer completely dependent on markets or supplies from outside the city, as they can meet some of their daily food needs from their own cultivated products. With agricultural products from urban farming, households have easier and cheaper access to nutritious food. The cost of purchasing groceries can be reduced, thereby increasing purchasing power and household consumption choices, especially for the lower middle economic group.

This is in line with the definition of household food security, which is a condition when households have sufficient physical, social, and economic access to safe, nutritious, and nutritional food for healthy and active living (Bappenas, 2020). Access to food is not only physical but also includes economic and social dimensions, as well as the sustainability of supply. In this context, urban farming plays an important role because it not only increases food availability and accessibility, but also strengthens the stability of supply and household food independence in a sustainable manner. Urban farming managed by the Women Farmers Group (KWT) has a strategic role in strengthening household food security.

The Women Farmers Group (KWT) is a participatory forum formed to empower women, especially in the field of agriculture and household-scale food management. The Women Farmers Group (KWT) plays a strategic role as a driving force for community-based urban farming. KWT has been proven to be able to strengthen household food security through various initiatives, such as vegetable cultivation in the yard, the use of household waste for compost, and healthy food processing training [7].

The Women Farmers Group (KWT) also functions as a forum for women's empowerment and social solidarity. With the direct involvement of women, urban farming activities become more sustainable and integrated with family nutritional needs. The active role of KWT in urban farming can increase household income, expand access to local food sources, and strengthen social networks at the community level.

Bukit Kecil District and Plaju District are two sub-districts in Palembang City that are dominated by residential and urban areas. Most of the people live in an environment with limited land, high dependence on food supplies from outside the city, and high expenditure for daily food consumption. Based on initial observations and data there are still a number of households that have not reached an adequate level of food security, especially in terms of access to fresh and nutritious food. One of the key factors in the development of urban farming at the local level is the Women Farmers Group (KWT). In addition, these activities encourage the participation of family members, increase knowledge about healthy food, and strengthen the social resilience of communities in urban environments [4]

Bukit Kecil and Plaju sub-districts were chosen as the research locations by considering several strategic aspects. First, these two sub-districts represent two different administrative areas in Palembang City, namely one sub-district from the Ilir (Bukit Kecil) area and one sub-district from the Ulu (Plaju) area. This selection is expected to provide a more diverse picture of the implementation and benefits of urban farming in two different regional contexts.

Second, the urban farming program in Bukit Kecil and Plaju Districts was both established in 2020 and until now has had a Farmer Women Group (KWT) that actively manages these activities. This condition facilitates research because researchers obtain relevant primary and secondary data.

Third, the two sub-districts have different environmental characteristics. Bukit Kecil District is located in the city center, dominated by commercial and office areas, so the main challenge in the development of urban farming is land limitations. Meanwhile, Plaju District is an area with a combination of dense settlements and industrial areas, so the challenge lies more in environmental quality and limited land utilization.

Fourth, there is support from different external parties in each location, which can affect the sustainability of the program. Urban farming in Bukit Kecil District receives support from Bank Rakyat Indonesia (BRI) and Pegadaian, while urban farming in Plaju District receives support from Pertamina. With a combination of regional representation, the same time of program establishment, the existence of active KWT, and differences in environmental characteristics, the selection of Bukit Kecil and Plaju Districts is expected to produce comprehensive and relevant research findings for the development of urban farming in Palembang City.

Bukit Kecil and Plaju sub-districts were chosen as the research locations because they both represent the characteristics of densely populated urban areas with high levels of land limitations, but on the other hand have an active urban farming program and community participation, especially KWT, which is active in growing vegetables, medicinal plants, and fruits on a household and community scale. The selection of locations in this study, namely Kampung Sayur Cempako and Kampung Proklam were chosen as the focus for "Analysis of the Role of Women Farmer Groups (KWT) in the Urban Farming Program to Increase Household Food Security in Bukit Kecil District and Plaju District, Palembang City".

2. Material and methods

2.1. Place and Time of Research

This research was carried out in Bukit Kecil and Plaju Districts. The selection of locations is carried out deliberately (purposeful). This location was chosen considering that these 2 sub-districts already have a Women Farmer Group (KWT) in the urban farming program. The implementation of this research in November 2025.

2.2. Research Methods

The method used in this study is the survey method, which is a method that is carried out directly to the research location, as well as conducting interviews using questionnaires as a tool for collecting basic data. It is hoped that this method can obtain factual information and information that occurs in the field through sampling a part of the population that can represent the whole of the Women Farmer Group (KWT) in the Urban Farming Program.

2.3. Sampling Method

The sampling method used in this study is the Census method. The census method or saturated sampling is a sample extraction technique where all members of the population are used as research samples [8]. The main reason for using the census method is that the number of the population involved in the study is relatively small (less than 100 people) and is still fully accessible, so that more accurate and comprehensive data can be obtained. In this case, the research population is all active members of the Women Farmers Group (KWT). The number of Cempako Women Farmers Group (KWT) in Bukit Kecil District is 27 members and the number of Barokah Women Farmers Group (KWT) in Plaju District is 13 members.

2.4. Data Collection Methods

The data collected in this study is sourced from primary and secondary data. Primary data is data obtained directly from observations in the field by interviewing respondents through questionnaire media. The interview is guided by a list of questions (questionnaires) that have been prepared in advance by the researcher. Meanwhile, secondary data is supporting data obtained from relevant sources such as from related agencies, books, the internet, and previous research reports.

2.5. Data Processing Methods

The strategy for developing urban farming programs to increase staple food security in Bukit Kecil and Plaju Districts, Palembang City, analyzed with SWOT analysis.

Figure 1 SWOT Analysis Chart

- Quadrant I: This is a very favorable situation, where the business condition has opportunities and strengths so that it can take advantage of existing opportunities. The strategy that must be applied in this condition is to support an aggressive growth policy (Growth oriented strategy).
- Quadrant II: Despite facing various threats, business conditions still have internal strength. The strategy that must be implemented is to use power to take advantage of long-term opportunities by means of a diversification strategy (product/service).
- Quadrant III: The business is facing enormous market opportunities, but on the other hand, it faces some internal constraints/weaknesses. The business conditions in quadrant 3 are similar to the Question Mark on the BCG matrix. The focus of this company's strategy is to minimize the company's internal problems so that it can seize more market opportunities.
- Quadrant IV: This is a very unfavorable situation, the business conditions face various internal threats and weaknesses.

3. Strategy for the Development of Women Farmer Groups in Urban Farming Activities

3.1. Internal Factors

Internal factor analysis was used to analyze internal factors that affect the development of Cempako and Barokah farmer women groups. The results of the analysis of internal factors will produce strengths and weaknesses which will then be used as a consideration in determining the development strategy of the Cempako and Barokah women farmer groups [9]. In this analysis, there are 4 strength factors, namely the majority of members are housewives so they have enough free time, long cultivation experience so that the technical skills of the members are more mature. The level of cohesiveness of members is high so that activities run effectively and directed, has a track record of achievements, such as the victory of Proklim at the provincial level and participation at the national level, while for weaknesses there are also 4 factors, namely Lack of innovation in processed products, so that the added value of crops is not optimal, Dependence on several active members, Dependence on government assistance and lack of initiative to find alternative funding sources, and Less optimal in the use of social media for the promotion and sale of crops.

3.2. External Factors

External factor analysis was used to analyze external factors that affect the development of Cempako and Barokah farmer women groups. The results of the analysis of external factors will produce opportunities and threats that are used as considerations in determining the development strategy of the Cempako and Barokah women farmer groups [10]. In this analysis, there are 4 opportunity factors, namely government support for urban farming and urban food security, market demand for fresh and organic vegetables continues to increase, KWT has the opportunity to become a role model for KWT because of the experience and achievements that have been achieved, the development of processed products while for threats there are also 4 factors, namely dependence on weather and environmental conditions that can affect productivity, Market competition or changes in assistance policies that may affect the continuity of the program, Member interest may decrease if crop yields are unstable, Market price fluctuations.

3.3. IFE and EFE Matrix for the Development of Women Farmer Groups

The IFE (Internal Factor Evaluation) matrix is used to evaluate internal factors, namely strengths and weaknesses [11]. The EFE (External Factor Evaluation) matrix is used to evaluate external factors that include opportunities and threats [12]. For more details on the IFE and EFE matrices in this study, see Table 2 and Table 3.

Table 1 IFE Matrix of KWT Cempako and KWT Barokah

No	Indicators	KWT Cempako			KWT Barokah		
		Weight	Rating	Score	Weight	Rating	Score
Strengths							
1.	The majority of members are housewives so they have enough free time	0.25	3.89	0.97	0.26	3.71	0.96
2.	Long cultivation experience so that the technical abilities of the members are more mature.	0.25	3.89	0.97	0.25	3.57	0.89
3.	The level of cohesiveness of the members is high so that the activity runs effectively and directed.	0.25	3.96	1.01	0.24	3.50	0.85
4	It has a track record of achievements, such as Proklm victories at the provincial level and participation at the national level.	0.25	3.85	0.95	0.25	3.57	0.89
Sum				3.90			3.59
Weakness							
1	The lack of innovation in processed products, so that the added value of crops is not optimal.	0.26	3.00	0.79	0.24	2.21	0.52
2	Dependence on multiple active members	0.26	2.93	0.75	0.24	2.21	0.52
3	Reliance on government assistance and lack of initiative to seek alternative funding sources.	0.25	2.81	0.69	0.26	2.43	0.63
4	Less than optimal in the use of social media for the promotion and sale of crops.	0.24	2.70	0.64	0.27	2.50	0.67
Sum				2.87			2.35

The results of the IFE matrix calculation for KWT Cempako and Barokah can be seen in Table 2. The score of KWT Cempako's strength is 3.90 while KWT Barokah's strength is 3.59 and KWT Cempako's weakness is 2.87, while KWT Barokah's weakness is 2.35. This shows that the internal situation of the Cempako and Barokah farmer women groups is strong enough to overcome the existing weaknesses. The difference from the total strength and weakness score of KWT Cempako is 1.03.

Table 2 EFE Matrix of KWT Cempako and KWT Barokah

No	Indicators	KWT Cempako			KWT Barokah		
		Weight	Rating	Score	Weight	Rating	Score
Opportunities							
1.	Government support for urban farming and urban food security is increasing	0.24	3.48	0.84	0.25	3.62	0.90
2.	Market demand for fresh and organic vegetables continues to increase	0.24	3.52	0.85	0.25	3.69	0.92
3.	KWT has the opportunity to become a role model for KWT because of the experience and achievements that have been achieved.	0.26	3.70	0.95	0.24	3.54	0.86
4	Development of processed products	0.26	3.70	0.95	0.25	3.69	0.94
Sum				3.60			3.62
Threats							
1	Dependence on weather and environmental conditions that can affect productivity.	0.24	2.22	0.53	0.22	2.08	0.45
2	Market competition or changes in aid policies that may affect the continuity of the program.	0.26	2.44	0.64	0.24	2.31	0.55
3	Member interest may decrease if crop yields are unstable	0.24	2.22	0.53	0.29	2.77	0.80
4	Market price fluctuations	0.26	2.44	0.64	0.26	2.46	0.63
Sum				2.34			2.43

The results of the EFE matrix calculation can be seen in Table 3. The score of the odds of KWT Cempako is 33.60 while the odds of KWT Barokah are 3.62. For the threat of KWT Cempako is 2.34, while the threat of KWT Barokah is 2.43. This shows that the Cempako and Barokah farmer women groups can make maximum use of existing opportunities to minimize existing threats. The difference from the total opportunity and threat score of KWT Cempako is 1.26 and the difference from the total opportunity and threat score of KWT Barokah is 1.19. The difference between strengths and weaknesses as well as opportunities and threats is used as coordinates to determine the development position of the Cempako and Barokah women farmer groups.

3.4. SWOT Analysis Diagram

The SWOT Analysis Diagram is a visual representation used to map four main aspects that affect the condition and development of the Women Farmers Group (KWT). This diagram maps four important elements that affect the sustainability and development of a group, namely internal strengths, internal weaknesses, and external threats. Through this mapping, it can be known how the organization responds [13].

In a SWOT (Strength, Weakness, Opportunity, Threat) analysis diagram visualized in the form of a cartesian diagram (X and Y axes), the axes represent the internal factors and external factors of an organization or project: X Axis (Horizontal): Describes the internal factors, which are the comparison between Strengths and Weaknesses. The stronger the value of strength versus weakness, the coordinate point will move in the right direction. Conversely, if the weakness is more dominant, the point is on the left side of the chart. Y-axis (Vertical): Describes external factors, which is the comparison between Opportunity and Threat. If the external odds are very large, the coordinate points move upwards. But when the threat is greater, the point moves down. The combined values on the X and Y axes are then placed in four quadrants [14].

Through the results of SWOT calculations on KWT Cempako and KWT Barokah, both groups showed the same tendency, namely being in a relatively favorable position. This explains that the urban farming program run by the two groups has a fairly good internal basis and a supportive external environment, so that the development strategy can be directed at strengthening the program, increasing the capacity of members, and optimizing the use of assistance and market

opportunities. For more details of the SWOT analysis diagram of KWT Cempako and KWT Barokah in this study, see Figure 4. and Figure 5.

Figure 2 Digram SWOT Analysis of KWT Cempako

Figure 3 Digram SWOT Analysis of KWT Barokah

Based on Figure 2., the results of the SWOT analysis show that the total score difference between strengths and weaknesses in KWT Cempako is 1.03, while the total score difference between opportunities and threats reaches 1.26. The positive value in both differences places KWT Cempako in Quadrant I, which is a position with strong internal conditions and a supportive external environment. This position illustrates that the group is at a very strategic point to grow, as it has adequate internal capacity as well as external opportunities that can be maximized.

Meanwhile, in Figure 3., the results of the analysis for KWT Barokah show that this group has a total difference in strength and weakness score of 1.24, as well as a difference in opportunities and threats of 1.19. Like KWT Cempako, this position also places KWT Barokah in Quadrant I, which means that this group is in a very ideal condition to carry out development. The dominant internal strength, combined with great external opportunities, shows that KWT Barokah is in the right phase to expand activities, increase production, utilize institutional assistance, and optimize the economic and social potential of urban farming programs. This condition emphasizes that KWT Barokah has the ability to continue to grow and innovate in line with the progressive strategies recommended for organizations in the same quadrant.

3.5. Alternative Analysis of Development Strategies with SWOT Matrix

The SWOT matrix analysis was used to formulate several alternative strategies that are in accordance with the internal and external conditions of the Cempako and Barokah farmer women groups. Some alternative strategies that can be developed through a SWOT matrix include S-O strategies, W-O strategies, S-T strategies, and W-T strategies. Based on the position analysis using the Grand Strategy, it can be seen that the position of the Cempako and Barokah farmer women groups is in quadrant I. The results of this analysis are a reference to determine alternative strategies for the development of Cempako and Barokah farmer women groups, namely the S-O (Strenght Opportunities) strategy. There are 4 alternative strategies in the development of Cempako and Barokah farmer women groups, including:

3.5.1. Strengthening Production and Capacity Building by Utilizing Government Support

Using the strength of cultivation experience, member cohesiveness, and track record of achievement to maximize opportunities in the form of government programs in the field of urban farming and food security. This strategy can be in the form of training in modern cultivation techniques, intensive assistance, assistance with infrastructure, and more productive land expansion or planting media. With strong experience, KWT has the opportunity to become a sustainable pilot model.

3.5.2. Processed Product Development and Commodity Diversification

The strength of the technical capabilities of the members and the solidity of the group can be combined with the opportunity of increasing market demand for organic products and fresh vegetables. This strategy focuses on the development of derivative/processed products (e.g. salad mixes, ready-to-cook vegetables, ready-to-use spices, improving quality and production standards so that KWT is able to meet the modern market.

3.5.3. Social Media Based Branding, Promotion, and Sales Optimization

The cohesiveness of the members and the track record of achievements can be used to build a positive image of KWT as a successful urban agricultural group. Furthermore, take advantage of large market opportunities by creating KWT's official marketing account, expanding the network of partnerships with food MSMEs, restaurants, hotels, and vegetable stores, and participating in local food exhibition events. This strategy will strengthen KWT's position as a role model in marketing urban farming products.

3.5.4. Development of KWT as an Education/Visit Center (Urban Farming Learning Center)

With the strength of long experience, cohesiveness, and achievements, plus great opportunities from government programs, KWT can be developed into a learning location for hydroponic agriculture and urban farming. These strategies can include training for the general public, schools, communities, and agencies, internship programs or comparative studies.

Based on the results of the SWOT analysis visualized through the Cartesian diagram, both at KWT Cempako and KWT Barokah, all research findings show that the two groups of women farmers are in Quadrant I, which is a position that describes superior internal strength and very open external opportunities [15]. The location of the strategic coordinates in Quadrant I indicates that KWT's internal conditions have been able to support the optimal use of opportunities, thus

encouraging the emergence of aggressive strategies in the form of product development, market expansion, integration, and program diversification.

Thus, the third hypothesis proposed in this study that the development strategy of the Women Farmers Group (KWT) in the urban farming program in Palembang City is in Quadrant I is proven to be in accordance with and in line with the results of the study. Both KWT Cempako and KWT Barokah show characteristics consistent with aggressive growth strategies, so that the hypothesis can be accepted and supported empirically. This finding also confirms that the urban farming program, supported by institutional strengthening and assistance from various parties, has placed the two KWTs in a very strategic position to continue to develop and expand their economic and social impact on the community.

4. Conclusion

The development strategy of KWT Cempako and KWT Barokah in the urban farming program in Palembang City is in quadrant 1. The location of the strategic coordinates in Quadrant I indicates that the internal conditions of KWT have been able to support the optimal use of opportunities. Local governments, SOEs, or partner institutions, it is expected to expand assistance programs and provide continuous assistance, not only in the aspects of production facilities, but also in capacity building, marketing, and institutional management. In addition, it is important to conduct periodic monitoring and evaluation so that the impact of assistance on increasing the role and empowerment of KWT can continue to be optimized

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of Conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study. Statement of

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